

Effect of Phosphorus Application on Yield and Nitrogen Uptake by Soya bean Varieties in Typic Chromustert

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Effect of phosphorus application at four levels was assessed in three soya bean varieties in a green house trial on a vertisol, deficient in phosphorus. The plant biomass, the seed yield and total uptake of nitrogen by plants increased with levels of P applied and with the advancement of age. The maximum N-uptake was obtained in seed with the highest treatment dose and it was found that there was a significant variation among varieties. The JS-2 variety absorbed maximum nitrogen in grain and straw at harvest.

PHOSPHORUS is known to effect positively the growth of leguminous crops, when they are grown on a soil deficient in this nutrient¹. Different authors have also reported an increase in nitrogen absorption with increasing phosphatic fertilizer application, since it is known to effect nitrogen metabolism and protein synthesis in legumes²⁻⁴.

The work presented in this investigation is to evaluate the yield and quality aspect of nitrogen uptake by soya bean varieties under varying doses of phosphorus fertilisation in Jabalpur soil.

Experimental

The surface soil was collected from the experimental area of J. N. Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Jabalpur. The soil was clayey and neutral in reaction (pH 7.2). The predominant clay mineral in this soil is montmorillonite with a high cation-exchange capacity (48 m.e./100 g). The level of available nitrogen (240 kg N/ha) as well as available phosphorus (10 kg P₂O₅/ha) was low and of available potassium (263 kg K₂O/ha) was medium. The soil type is classed as typic chromustert.

The soil sample (10 kg) was filled in each of the 36 pots lined internally with polythene sheet to prevent leaching. Phosphorus was applied at the rate of 40, 80 and 120 kg P₂O₅/ha as single superphosphate. A basal application of 40 kg K₂O/ha as muriate of potash and 20 kg N/ha as urea was also given. The soya bean varieties JS-2, Gaurav and Punjab-1 were grown up to maturity and irrigated as and when required. The pots were arranged in the green house in completely randomised design and treatments were replicated thrice. The plant samples were taken at various physiological stages of the crop growth. At harvest, grain and straw samples were taken separately. The plant samples

were washed, dried and weighed for yield and then ground for estimation of nutrient. The nitrogen concentration was estimated by modified improved Kjeldahl method^{5,6}.

Results and Discussion

A perusal of the data in Table 1 shows that the plant biomass and seed yield of soybean increased by enhancing the doses of P upto 120 kg. All these effects can be attributed to the fact that initially the soil itself was not capable of supplying the nutrients in an amount adequate for the vigorous growth of plants, and as soon as the deficiency is made up, higher yield was obtained due to the supply of P and its priming effect on the release of other nutrients in the soil^{7,8}. The soybean varieties also differed in their performance with respect to plant biomass and seed yield. The variety JS-2 recorded highest seed yield (10.96 g) while Punjab-1 produced highest straw yield (13.53 g). Similar response was observed by Kesavan and Morachan⁹.

The perusal of the data in Table 2 shows that phosphorus application had a pronounced influence on quality aspect of crop pertaining to nitrogen metabolism through increased symbiotically fixed nitrogen supply and ultimately the protein synthesis^{1,9,10}. At harvest, the nitrogen uptake was more in seed and less in straw. This higher seed nitrogen uptake might be a result of transformation and translocation of nitrogenous compounds from shoot, leading to the formation seed protein^{4,11}. This may naturally lead to the depletion of nitrogen uptake (content) in straw. Secondly, a low nitrogen uptake in straw could be the result of the reduced synthetic capacity as well as increased protein degradation^{1,11}.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS APPLICATION ON DRY MATTER YIELD (g/pot)

	P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha				Mean	Effect	Sem. ±	CD at 5%
	P ₀	P ₄₀	P ₈₀	P ₁₂₀				
30 day stage								
JS-2	4.33	4.58	5.35	5.47	4.92	—	—	—
Gaurav	3.73	4.10	4.56	5.11	4.87	P	0.14	0.41
Punjab-1	3.53	5.21	5.67	5.73	5.03	—	—	—
Mean	3.86	4.61	5.19	5.48	—	V	0.12	0.85
Flowering stage								
JS-2	7.52	10.27	12.06	12.65	10.62	—	—	—
Gaurav	8.87	11.18	11.80	12.84	10.92	P	0.26	0.75
Punjab-1	8.06	9.76	11.66	11.55	10.35	—	—	—
Mean	7.98	10.40	11.84	12.18	—	V	0.22	NS
Harvesting stage								
<i>Grain</i>								
JS-2	9.19	10.83	11.94	12.39	10.96	—	—	—
Gaurav	8.97	10.02	11.57	12.84	10.72	P	0.24	0.71
Punjab-1	8.47	10.68	11.54	12.54	10.79	—	—	—
Mean	8.87	10.82	11.68	12.42	—	V	0.21	NS
<i>Straw</i>								
JS-2	10.17	11.90	14.55	14.93	12.98	—	—	—
Gaurav	9.85	12.09	18.78	14.76	12.62	P	0.22	0.65
Punjab-1	11.32	12.94	14.54	15.14	13.53	—	—	—
Mean	10.41	12.88	14.80	15.03	—	V	0.19	0.57

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PHOSPHORUS APPLICATION ON UPTAKE OF NITROGEN (mg/pot)

	P levels kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha				Mean	Effect	Sem. ±	CD at 5%
	P ₀	P ₄₀	P ₈₀	P ₁₂₀				
30 day stage								
JS-2	61.81	74.93	102.86	109.94	87.38	—	—	—
Gaurav	40.86	56.54	75.92	87.02	64.94	P	3.29	9.59
Punjab-1	46.53	38.78	108.61	113.43	88.84	—	—	—
Mean	49.78	73.48	94.93	103.46	—	V	2.85	8.30
Flowering stage								
JS-2	91.37	156.34	212.48	237.80	174.49	—	—	—
Gaurav	106.05	183.03	257.78	289.19	208.99	P	6.01	17.52
Punjab-1	112.54	157.81	228.05	233.72	183.65	—	—	—
Mean	103.82	165.55	232.10	255.22	—	V	5.20	15.17
Harvesting stage								
<i>Grain</i>								
JS-2	504.46	713.58	869.38	926.24	753.40	—	—	—
Gaurav	345.71	493.65	655.48	803.86	575.80	P	14.11	41.72
Punjab-1	436.36	714.58	814.95	896.65	715.18	—	—	—
Mean	428.51	640.58	779.93	876.75	—	V	12.22	35.61
<i>Straw</i>								
JS-2	74.12	117.41	186.19	204.86	145.89	—	—	—
Gaurav	35.92	61.30	88.77	103.56	72.88	P	3.35	9.76
Punjab-1	53.18	75.89	113.86	133.08	95.26	—	—	—
Mean	54.40	84.86	129.94	148.83	—	V	2.90	8.45

The nitrogen uptake in JS-2 was higher in seed as well as in straw. Thus it established its superiority in terms of protein content over other varieties. Similar responses were observed in soya bean^{4,9}.

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